

Nasal Glial Heterotopia in An Infant: Presentation of Case

Radhi Med El Hafed*, Douimi Loubna, Chebaatha Anas, Youssef Oukessou, Mahtar Mohamed, Redalah Larbi.Abada, Rouadi Sami, Roubal Mohamed

Department of ENT Head and Neck Surgery, Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, Hassan II University, Casablanca, Morocco

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***Corresponding author:** Radhi Med El Hafed, Department of ENT Head and Neck Surgery, Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, Hassan II University, Casablanca, Morocco

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Glial heterotopia is a rare congenital anomaly rather than a true tumor, usually located in the nose and nasopharynx, due to which the condition is also referred to as nasal glioma.

Case Presentation: we report the case of nasal glial heterotopia, the ex-nasal type; in a 4-year-old patient. Physical examination shows an obviously visible mass, painless, located in the dorsum of the nose. Investigations were completed by computed tomography scan (CT) and MRI which was suggestive of nasal glial heterotopia, The lesion is removed entirely with caution under endoscopic control.

Clinical discussion: Nasal glial heterotopia is a rare congenital malformation, in which a mass of mature glial cells are found in a location outside the central nervous system, Surgical removal remains the gold standard treatment.

Conclusion: Nasal glial heterotopia is a rare anomaly that requires total surgical excision in order to avoid recurrences.

Keywords: Nasal glial heterotopia, Nasal glioma, congenital anomaly.

INTRODUCTION

Nasal glial heterotopia is a rare developmental abnormality seen in a wide age group but typically at birth or in early childhood.^[1]

CT scan and MRI are required before excision to exclude an encephalocele, which requires different type of surgery. Its treatment consists of a complete and early surgical resection, to avoid a further tumor growth, which would aggravate the symptoms.^[2]

We report the rare case of an infant with nasal glial heterotopia treated by endoscopic surgery.

This study has been reported in accordance with the SCARE criteria.^[3]

CASE REPORT

A 4-year-old girl, with no past medical or surgical history, was referred to our department for a swelling of the dorsum of the nose, gradually increasing in size.

In the interrogation nothing was found, the patient denied fever, or any other sign neither nasal sign nor respiratory ones. However Physical examination was unremarkable despite an obviously visible mass, painless, located in the dorsum of the nose, firm of consistency, moveable to deep planes, with a normal underlying skin. This mass measured approximately 1.5 centimeters (Figure 1). No cervical lymph node was found. Nasal examination doesn't reveal any abnormalities. Soft tissues ultrasound shows a swelling of the root of the nose lateralized to the left, without its own capsule, suggesting a benign lesion.

Investigations were completed by computed tomography scan (CT) and MRI which was suggestive of nasal glial heterotopia; oval and well limited, in hypo signal T1 T2 and diffusion. It enhances homogeneously and peripherally after injection of contrast product, measuring 12x11 mm extended over 12 mm. No radiographic evidence of a bony abnormality in the nasal cavity, or base of the skull was documented (Figure 2,3).

Figure 1

Figure 2: CT scan images showing a mass of the dorsum of the nose well limited with no bony reaction.

Figure 3: Magnetic Resonance Imaging of the patient: axial view through the tumor.

Therefore, resection of the nasal lesion was performed using a RETHI incision

Figure 4: Peroperative view of the incision performed.

The lesion is removed entirely with caution under endoscopic control. No sign of bone erosion was noted, nor cerebrospinal fluid leak at the time of the surgery (Figure 5, 6). The surgery was made by ENT professor

Figure 5: Left: Intraoperative view of the excision of the lesion; Right: After excision of the lesion.

Figure 6: View of the operative piece

A reconstruction by conchal cartilage in double plate was carried out, thus allowing to define a good shape of the nasal pyramid.

The patient and his family were satisfied for the result.

The patient presented no recurrence during the 2 years of follow-up

Figure 7: Full and profil view of the patient after surgery

DISCUSSION

Nasal glial heterotopia is a rare congenital malformation, in which a mass of mature glial cells are found in a location outside the central nervous system. It was firstly reported by Reid in 1852, and the term of glial heterotopia was elaborated by Schmidt in 1900.^[4]

The pathogenesis of glial heterotopia has not yet been fully elucidated, yet it does not exhibit familial heredity and is not typically associated with other congenital malformations.^[5]

Glial heterotopia can occur in several sites, including the scalp, orbit, the nasal cavity, middle ear and mastoid, soft palate, tongue base, and other sites. Since it occurs mostly in the nose, this disease has been called nasal glial heterotopia.^[6]

It can be divided into: the “in-nasal type” located within the nasal cavity; the “ex-nasal type” located in the subcutaneous tissues of the nose; and the “mixed type” present in both these locations.^[7]

More than 90% of patients are diagnosed within the age of 3 to 4 years old. The male to female ratio is about 3:2. Preoperative examination typically consists of a CT scan and an MRI to evaluate an intracranial extension of the lesion, to determine its nature and to identify a bone defect if existed.^[8,9]

MRI provides more information concerning soft tissues than CT and is useful for identifying intracranial connections. In most clinical practices, MRI has replaced CT as the first choice and is often the only preoperative imaging study required to evaluate newborns and infants with congenital frontonasal masses.^[9]

Surgical removal remains the gold standard treatment. In fact, early surgical management is preferred to avoid further tumor enlargement. Indeed, surgery should be as complete as possible to avoid recurrences; these last have been reported in 4% to 10% after surgery.^[10]

Close and regular follow-up after surgery is important to detect recurrences and treat them in a timely manner.

CONCLUSION

Nasal glial heterotopia is a rare anomaly that requires total surgical excision in order to avoid recurrences. Preoperatively, CT scan and MRI are usually performed to determine whether the lesion has an intracranial communication in order to prevent cerebrospinal fluid leakage and eventually meningitis. Close follow-up is highly recommended to detect recurrences.

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